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Sustainable Solutions to Land Scarcity for Social Housing in South African Cities *Faranani Gethe*¹; *Prisca Simbanegavi*¹; *Pride Ndlovu*¹ and *Malcolm Roy Weaich*¹

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Abstract

Land scarcity near economic hubs in South Africa poses significant challenges to developing inclusive and sustainable cities, particularly for social housing. The purpose of this research is to explore practical strategies to address land shortages and high costs while promoting social housing within proximity to urban centres. A qualitative research design was employed, involving semi-structured interviews with housing development experts from Johannesburg, Cape Town, and Tshwane. The study used thematic analysis to identify recurring themes from expert perspectives. The key findings reveal five actionable strategies: (i) public-private partnerships (PPPs) for land acquisition, (ii) long-term municipal land leases, (iii) repurposing decayed buildings into low-income housing, (iv) integrating social housing into mixed-use developments, and (v) implementing government tax incentives for social housing in greenfield projects. These strategies emphasize leveraging existing urban spaces, innovative financing, and policy interventions to reduce development costs and foster inclusivity. The study concludes that overcoming land scarcity for social housing requires a multi-stakeholder approach integrating urban planning, innovative financial models, and regulatory support. By adopting these strategies, municipalities can mitigate spatial inequality, reduce commuting distances, and enhance the quality of life for low-income residents. Future research should focus on assessing the long-term viability and scalability of these interventions.

Key words: Land Scarcity; Social Housing; Sustainable Cities; Economic Hubs; South Africa.

Introduction

Housing inadequacy can be traced back to apartheid that caused spatial inequality in South Africa (Shahaboonin et al. 2023). During apartheid, segregation policies created townships where 43% of nearly sixty million people live on major city outskirts (Todes and Turok, 2017; Ogra & Onatu, 2013). This outskirts location is a key contributor to high poverty level (Turok, 2018). Literature shows that 52% of jobs are found in urban areas which only houses 34% of the workforce, an undeniable housing poverty that stimulates informal settlements closer to economic hubs (Turok and Borel-Saladin (2013). Staying on the outskirts of cities has great disadvantages. Popoola, Magidimisha-Chipungu & Chipungu (2022) find distance was a predictor of credit access among rural households in peri-urban villages and rural communities in the Southwestern region of Nigeria. This highlights the need for social housing, which is different from subsidised housing in the outskirts of metropolitan areas (Olanrewaju, Anavhe, & Hai1, 2016).

Government in Hong Kong, targets increasing housing supply via increasing supply of land closer to urban centres (Huang, Shen & Zheng, 2015). Government over the last decade has been making means of providing basic housing and land to millions of South Africans in need of shelter. These efforts, however, come short of eliminating the issue of unavailable social housing calling for a greater intervention to facilitate developing housing for the poor (Turok, Scheba, & Visagie, 2022). In South Africa, the closer land is to highways and economic hubs, the higher the bid rent is. This makes land closer to economic hubs more expensive given that land price is a residual value, taking its price from more profitable developments (Massyn et al. 2015). Given these costs associated with acquiring land, developers use 'highest and best use'

criteria to develop real estate which often crowd out social housing. This is because development focuses on buildings that bring better returns to cover the cost of land. This stimulates vertical development. This urban economics concept has dictated the outskirts location of RDP housing in the outskirts of most cities in South Africa. This has also resulted in insufficient development of social housing within the economic hubs leading to illegal occupation of abandoned residential buildings in the cities and rapid informal settlement erected on privately owned land. Little is known about how to circumvent the high cost of land within the economic hubs to expedite the development of social housing. In South Africa, there is need for the department of Human Settlement to find better interventions to achieve the goal of inclusive cities for social housing which is derailed by the cost of land closer to economic hubs. Surprisingly, Othman & Mia (2008) found an unwillingness by government to release sufficient suitable land for housing developments.

The aim of this study is to explore sustainable solutions to land scarcity for social housing in South African cities. Specifically, it seeks to (i) identify the key challenges that hinder the development of social housing in well-located areas, (ii) examine expert perspectives on feasible interventions, and (iii) recommend strategies that municipalities and developers can adopt to promote inclusive housing near economic hubs. Accordingly, the study is guided by the following research questions: *What are the main challenges of providing social housing in well-located urban areas? How do housing experts perceive potential solutions? What strategies can enhance the integration of social housing into economic hubs?.*

Literature Review

This literature review explores the topic on Social Housing (SH) and Economic Hubs (EHs), focusing on the opportunities and challenges associated with its developments. In a less inclusive ways, SH has been developed in the outskirts of cities. These developments are fragmented and do not promote integration and transformation (Onatu, 2012). Part of the problem is that the land closer to economic hubs is significantly more expensive than land on the outskirts where housing developers opt to develop there for the pursuit of profits. This is because land price is a residual value which is higher when a development is more profitable. Government has a role to play in redistributing land through its policies and intervention (Musakwa, Tshesane, & Kangethe, 2017; Makinde, 2014).

There is growing recognition of the potential benefits of developing SH in proximity to economic hubs as high-density rental housing (Massyn et al. 2015; Gunter, 2013). To promote development within economic hubs, municipalities should permit flexible building densities to maximize on shortage of land (Yan, Ge, & Wu, 2014). The benefits include improved access to employment opportunities, enhanced access to services and amenities, reduced transportation costs and commuting time and inclusivity that comes from possible social integration and reduced stigmatization (Simbanegavi, 2019). Thus, SH built closer to EHs avoids the negatives associated with informal settlements such as negative impacts on health (Nyashanu et al. 2020). Wider benefits of housing closer to economic hubs include access to employment, education, healthcare, and cultural amenities, positively impacting on residents' quality of life and social mobility.

A good example of a successful example of an SH development near EHs is the Marabastad Townlands SH in Tshwane. The multimillion-rand social housing project consists of 1 200 mixed units and covers residents of Tshwane who do not qualify for government subsidy houses

nor earn enough to qualify for a home loan. Beneficiaries of this SH development earn between R1 500 and R15 000 per month.

Figure 1: Social Housing in Tshwane

Source: Mathonsi Thobile, African News Agency (ANA)

Such examples have been achieved through innovative financing models and partnerships. Innovative financing models such as Land Value Capture (LVC) can be used to circumvent the budget constraints that exist in government (Gethe et al. 2023). Urban planning and policy are moving towards incorporating SH in urban regeneration plans, zoning and land use policies to facilitate social housing in central areas. There is also an angle on sustainability and environmental considerations where reduced carbon footprint and transportation emissions, sustainable building design and energy efficiency and urban greening and access to open spaces (Gethe & Simbanegavi, 2024; Liao, Ren, & Li, 2023).

There exist challenges of locating SH closer to ESHs. These include land availability and high cost, gentrification and displacement risks, NIMBYism (Not in My Backyard) and infrastructure and services provision. This is the reason sometimes Greenfields become default locations for SH. Mixed Use (MUDs) in greenfield can counter these challenges whereby a thriving ecosystem which contains the SH, public transportation and infrastructure can be a solution to housing the poor such as Cosmo City (Simbanegavi & Ijasa, 2022; Onatu, 2012). Such developments proved to save on costs of development in terms of bulk infrastructure that is already in place. This review of literature shows a knowledge gap in developers' perspectives and experiences on how to promote the development of SH closer to ESHs.

Methodology

Guidelines from Saunders et al. (2016), informed the study to use qualitative research design to investigate ways to deal with shortage of land for social housing given that such land is crowded out by the theory of highest and best use in most cities. Following approval of the research proposal by the Witwatersrand University Ethics Committee, four housing development experts were interviewed as a pilot study to test the research guideline (Majid et al. 2017). The interview guide was informed by the literature on previous studies on housing development (Sathvik, Krishnaraj, & Awuzie, 2023). Information from the pilot study helped to improve the questions specified in the research guideline that was extended to purposively selected experts in housing development, recruited through direct contacts from Johannesburg, Cape Town, and Tswane Metros (about 12 participants were interviewed). These participants had experience in sourcing land for housing development. Through the interview guideline, semi-structured questions were formulated and used to prompt viewpoints about land for social housing. Interviews were conducted as a flexible instrument to interact with expert stakeholders who are involved in developing low-cost housing in South Africa.

Data collection

Researchers sent letters and information sheets to the organisations inviting housing developers to take part in the research study. Only those who had agreed to take part in the research study had their names and telephone contacts forwarded to the researchers to organise interview dates and times where they would sign a consent form prior to taking part in the interview. The participants had an opportunity to read the information sheet and ask questions to get more clarity on this research where they had an option to withdraw from the study at any time without giving reasons. The interviews lasted for one hour and were conducted in English.

Data analysis

The tape-recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim, and all transcriptions were read back to the participants to verify the accuracy of the main points through Microsoft teams. All confirmed data was recorded into NVivo, a software that helps organise data for a robust thematic analysis. Repeatedly reading transcriptions made it possible to identify concerns about participants experiences that were important to the participant regarding land for housing. This made it possible to hear and understand the participant's views in their own words and keep their experience at the centre of the study. Relevant parts were summarised and assigned codes representing the researcher's interpretation of participants' viewpoints. Through cluster analysis, the identified codes were seen to cluster collectively into themes. A summary of these five themes constituted the final output of this research study and are presented in the section that follows.

Findings and Discussion

The paper finds five research themes on how to deal with land scarcity for social housing in metros listed below.

- i. Release of land for social housing through PPPs
- ii. Use of long term land leases by municipalities
- iii. Conversion of decayed buildings into low income housing for rent.
- iv. Design Mixed Use Developments (MUDs)

- v. Use of government tax incentives social housing in Greenfields.

Release of land for social housing through PPPs

There is extra pressure on the cost of land closer to economic hubs which makes it more expensive. This has led to most housing developers opting to buy cheaper land in the outskirts and developing it for social housing in partnerships with municipalities. This has resulted in disgruntled citizens who view this as failure to build inclusive cities. The advice mainly given is that through Public Private Partnership more houses can be rolled out. Housing developers are of the viewpoint that supply of land closer to economic hubs for social housing through PPPs. The bond between public and private investment must be stronger where both parties contribute to housing development that will sustain in the future where both parties can take advantage of the provision of social housing. Land is too expensive in the inner cities however municipalities can create a policy that makes municipalities give/donate land in inner cities for social housing through 20-30 year-long leases after which social housing is taken over by municipalities as an asset. This will stimulate construction of social housing closer to economic hubs by private developers bringing in the much needed supply that is need.

Use of long-term land leases by municipalities

Data suggested that the government and municipalities must make land available for social low-cost housing, and for the land that belongs to the municipality like those that are under construction near Marabastad in the City of Tshwane. This concurs with Molefe & Nkhahle (2019) who suggested that 'municipalities should have the right of first refusal to acquire state-owned land and land owned by State-Owned Entities (SOEs) when the State and SOEs intend to dispose of their land'. Based on the respondents regarding the cost of land near the economic hubs the Metropolitan Municipalities must work together with HDA to identify land that belongs to the city and give it to social housing agents for the development of social houses. Social housing is to ensure social and decent housing and to be part of urban regeneration. If government provides land within or closer to the economic hubs at a lesser value to social housing developers for the construction of social housing will better the revenue of the developers. Though this might be a solution in theory it is not practical because of the economic unfeasibility it poses. An alternative would be the government allocating specific plots of available land they own for the development of low-cost housing. This is called the eminent domain, and it is for the benefit of the public. The government needs to come up with laws and policies that will make land social for houses. All other metropolitan municipalities must just emulate what is done by the city of Cape Town and make land available for social housing and subsidised low-cost housing. For lower commuting costs it is highly recommended that the development of such housing be increased in centralized economic areas. There is land that belongs to the municipalities in the inner cities that is lying idle. Government must give this land to SHIs so that it can be developed into social housing near economic hubs.

Conversion of decayed buildings into low-income housing for rent.

Urban renewal can be a solution to lack of social housing in inner cities where existing dilapidated buildings can be regenerated into rental housing by the urban poor (Gethe & Simbanegavi, 2024) These options include converting abandoned buildings into decent living spaces, seems to be more feasible. This is a good opportunity as most owners of these buildings, in most cases, do not have funds to renovate these buildings. Thus, government can partly fund renovations of these buildings and have them converted into social rental units with private-

sector management. The Maboneng Precinct in Johannesburg inner city is an example of successful development that shows how the cost of land need not be a limiting factor in curbing the insufficient supply of decent housing close to the inner cities of Gauteng. Other metropolitan municipalities need to adopt the strategies that are used by the City of Tshwane and the City of Cape Town where some of the buildings that belong to the municipality are being converted to social housing institutions. Social housing can also be part of solving the problem as it is done in the City of Tshwane where the city gives a 20-year lease to the social housing developers like Yeast City Housing and in the City of Cape Town. Social housing is to ensure social and decent housing and to be part of urban regeneration. Most respondents agreed that people won't take a long trip to places of work, shopping centres, and government facilities if they are closer to the economic hubs. This study indicates that there is a high land cost near the economy, especially around Gauteng Metropolitan Municipalities. The city of Tshwane is giving some of the building that belongs to the municipality to the social housing developers on a 20-year lease agreement. The land is privately owned by individuals who don't want to give it to the subsidized low-cost housing for development they are selling it in small portions at a higher price.

Mixed Use Developments (MUDs)

While developers see the need for developing social housing closer to economic hubs, they shy away because the rate of return on their investment would prove to be very low. Most respondents agreed that people will not take long trips to places of work, shopping centres and government facilities if they are closer to the economic hubs. Participants view Mixed-Use Developments (MUDs) as a solution to promoting housing closer to economic hubs on the condition that incentives attached to MUDs will unlock cross-subsidization possibilities of some real estate asset classes such as retail, office space to the social housing asset. Redefining economic hubs may also be that the same infrastructure that is found in the inner city may be brought closer to the people on the outskirts, thus promoting more job opportunities and an effective transport system to allow people to commute from their homes to their places of work with ease.

Use of government tax incentives social housing in Greenfields.

Government should assist private developers developing on private land with tax rebates to bring the associated cost of acquiring land for social housing down. This can be in any form ranging from reduced bulk contributions, rates and taxes, tax rebates. Discussions elaborated that indeed land cost is the challenge when it comes to developing subsidised houses near or within the economic hubs. Other strategies have been applied as a plan of providing subsidised houses near or within the economic hubs while the cost of land is high. The challenges of developing subsidised houses near or within economic hubs are more or land related. This means that; the land is highly protected, and the owners of the land are not always willing to give away land without selling it. Therefore, the land policy focuses more on the protection of the owner without considering the public.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Land cost is still the major problem in the development of subsidised low-cost housing near the economic hubs of most metros in South Africa. The Gauteng Metropolitan Municipalities together with housing departments and government entities who are involved in the

subsidised low-cost housing and land for human settlement such as Housing Development Agency must come up with a plan that will involve the participation of private landowners and NGOs that are involved in the future of subsidised low-cost housing development in Gauteng Metropolitans.

The paper recommends that municipalities should give 20-year leases to social housing institutions that can develop low-income housing for rent (social housing) in South Africa. The state may need to investigate adopting methods used in other countries for long-term leasing of the land for housing development purposes. The lease-term turns out to be cheaper for the developers to acquire hectares of land as opposed to buying them at a high cost from the state or open market. With these houses, most people will not take long trips to places of work, shopping centres, and government facilities within the cities. Finding solutions to inclusive housing through land discourse is the main contribution and novelty of this research.

While the study provides valuable insights into strategies for addressing land scarcity for social housing, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the research adopted a qualitative approach with a relatively small sample size of experts from three metropolitan municipalities. As such, the findings may not capture the full diversity of perspectives across all South African cities or reflect broader national dynamics. Second, the study relied on self-reported experiences and perceptions of housing experts, which may carry subjective biases. Third, the focus was primarily on metropolitan areas, potentially overlooking unique challenges and opportunities in secondary cities or rural contexts. Lastly, the study did not undertake a quantitative assessment of the financial or policy feasibility of the proposed interventions, which limits the ability to generalise their scalability and long-term impact.

Future studies could expand on these findings by incorporating larger samples, mixed-method approaches, and comparative analyses across different regions. Quantitative modelling of costs, benefits, and long-term outcomes of proposed strategies would also strengthen the evidence base for policy and practice.

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No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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References

Gethe, F., Simbanegavi, P. and Ndlovu, P., 2023. Creating inclusive cities through the successful implementation of land value capture in South Africa. *Journal of Inclusive cities and Built environment*, 3(6), pp.73-83.

Gethe, F. & Simbanegavi, P., 2024. Balancing Urban Regeneration to prevent displacement – A conceptual Strategy for Inclusivity in South Africa. *AfRES 2024 conference Proceedings*. Zambia, 10 -13 September 2024, Pg 431- 439.

Huang, J., Shen, G. Q. & Zheng, H. W., 2015. Is insufficient land supply the root cause of the housing shortage? Empirical evidence from Hong Kong. *Habitat International*, 3 July, Volume 49, pp. 538 - 546.

Liao, H., Ren, R. and Li, L., 2023. Existing building renovation: a review of barriers to economic and environmental benefits. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(5), p.4058.

Mathonsi Thobile, *African News Agency (ANA)*. Accessed: 20 June 2023. [Marabastad Townlands social housing project beneficiaries urged to pay deposit or risk losing housing units \(iol.co.za\)](https://www.iol.co.za/news/south-africa/marabastad-townlands-social-housing-project-beneficiaries-urged-to-pay-deposit-or-risk-losing-housing-units-2023-06-20)

Molefe, N. & Nkhahle, S. 2019. Municipal urban land release and acquisition – SALGA's proposals to facilitate spatial transformation and inclusive economic growth through efficient urban land governance and management approaches. *Town and Regional Planning*, no.75, pp. 3-5.

Musakwa, W., Tshesane, R. M. & Kangethe, M., 2017. The strategically located land index support system for human settlements land reform in South Africa. *Cities*, 4 August, Volume 60, pp. 91 - 101.

Nyashanu, M., Simbanegavi, P. and Gibson, L., Exploring the impact of COVID-19 pandemic lockdown on informal settlements in Tshwane Gauteng Province, South Africa. *Glob Public Health* [Internet] 2020 [online]

Ogra, A. & Onatu, G., 2013. Metropolitan Housing Development in Urban Fringe Areas - A Case Study of Three Metropolitan Cities of South Africa: Johannesburg, Ekuruleni, and Tshwane. *2nd International Conference on Infrastructure Development in Africa (ICIDA)*, March. pp. 17 - 19.

Olanrewaju, A. L., Anavhe, P. & Hai1, T. K., 2016. A framework for social housing governance for the Nigerian Property Market. *Science Direct Procedia Engineering*, p. 307 – 314.

- Onatu, G. O., 2012. Sustainable Land Use and Development: Perspective on Cosmo City, Johannesburg, South Africa. *Sustainable Development and Environmental Protection*, Vol.2 No.1.
- Othman, A. A. E. & Mia, B., 2008. Corporate social responsibility for solving the housing problem for the poor in South Africa. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 5(3), pp. 237 - 257.
- Popoola, A.A., Magidimisha-Chipungu, H.H. and Chipungu, L., 2022. Profiling the wellbeing of residents in peri-urban villages and rural communities. *African Journal of Development Studies*, 12(1), p.267.
- Shahaboonin, F., David, O.O. and Van Wyk, A., 2023. Historic Spatial Inequality and Poverty along Racial Lines in South Africa. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 13(1), p.102.
- Sathvik, S., Krishnaraj, L. and Awuzie, B.O., 2023. Establishing the root causes of unsafe behaviours among construction workers: an integrative interpretive structural modelling analysis. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), p.7006.
- Simbanegavi, P., Ijasan, K., (2022). Does inclusive housing development depress Neighbourhood house prices? A case study of Cosmo City, Johannesburg, South Africa. *Journal of Inclusive Cities & The Built Environment (JICBE)*. Vol. 2, No. 3. *Urban Health and Spatial Development*. DOI <https://doi.org/10.54030/2788-564X/2022/v2s3a3>
- Simbanegavi, P (2019). Effects of Mixed Income Housing on Neighbourhood House Prices and Investment Guidelines for Future Inclusive Developments in South Africa. PhD Dissertation. The University of the Witwatersrand.
- Turok, I., Scheba, A. and Visagie, J., 2022. Can social housing help to integrate divided cities? *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 15(1), pp.93-116.
- Todes, A., Turok, I. (2018), Spatial inequalities and policies in South Africa: Place-based or people-centred? *Progress in Planning*, 123, 1-31
- Turok, I. (2018), Worlds Apart: Spatial Inequalities in South Africa. In: Smith, M.N. *Confronting Inequality: The South African Crisis*. Johannesburg: *Jacana Media*. p129-151.
- Turok, I., Borel-Saladin, J. (2013), Is urbanization in South Africa on a sustainable trajectory? *Development Southern Africa*, 31(5), 675-691.
- Yan, S., Ge, X. J. & Wu, Q., 2014. Government intervention in the land market and its impacts on land supply and new housing supply: Evidence from major Chinese markets. *Habitat International*, Issue 44, pp. 517 - 527.